

EXAMINING THE GAPS IN TEACHER-PARENT COLLABORATION IN SPECIAL NEEDS EDUCATION UNDER CBC IN NYERI COUNTY

Akinyi Grace Atieno

Department of Psychology and Educational Foundations, School of Education, Karatina University, Kenya.

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Abstract: Successful implementation of a Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) in Kenya in primary schools greatly depends on the Teacher–Parent Partnership (TPP). CBC is a well-modelled form of education that provides opportunities for parents to take part in the education of their children. The teachers expect a wellmodelled working relationship with each playing their role effectively for the realisation of good academic outcomes for learners with special needs. Empowerment of this partnership is inevitable, yet this is a resource that has remained underutilised. The teachers cited frustrations as the parents appeared not aware of their enormous role in the learning process both at home and school. The objective of the study was to establish the detriments of effective TPP in special primary school in Nyeri County, Kenya. The researcher adopted Epstein’s Model of parental involvement in the implementation of CBC. The study adopted a descriptive survey design method.

Keywords: Competence based curriculum Education Partnership Special needs

INTRODUCTION

Successful implementation of a Competence Based Curriculum (CBC) in Kenya in primary schools greatly depends on the Teacher–Parent Partnership (TPP). CBC is a well-modelled form of education that provides opportunities for parents to take part in the education of their children. The teachers expect a wellmodelled working relationship with each playing their role effectively for the realisation of good academic outcomes for learners with special needs. Empowerment of this partnership is inevitable, yet this is a resource that has remained underutilised. The teachers cited frustrations as the parents appeared not aware of their enormous role in the learning process both at home and school. The objective of the study was to establish the detriments of effective TPP in special primary school in Nyeri County, Kenya. The researcher adopted Epstein’s Model of parental involvement in the implementation of CBC. The study adopted a descriptive survey design method. A target sample of 47 teachers and 47 parents’ class representatives was used to obtain a sample of 14 class teachers and 14 parents (30%). Questionnaires for teachers and interview schedules for parents were used to collect data. The collected data were corrected, edited and analysed using the Statistical Package for Social Science. The results were presented using frequency tables, charts, and graphs. The results revealed that parents were not aware of the roles in the implementation of CBC apart from paying fees and attending meetings when called upon. The teachers also reported that major detriments were affecting

the partnership including gaps in the policies, lack of proper training on the skills, and pressure of completing the syllabus among others. The study thus recommends that there should be a policy that guides the partnership, a TPP manual for dealing with parents, and retooling of teachers on how to work with parents in the implementation of CBC. Empirical research indicates that parental involvement practices correlate with several positive results for children, including enhanced school performance, interpersonal skills and student motivation (Fan & Williams, 2010; Topor et al., 2010; Boonk et al., 2018; Otani, 2020; Farooq & Asim, 2020; Cosso, von Suchodoletz & Yoshikawa, 2022; Xiong et al., 2021; Kerei, Nangithia & Mwai). As a result of the positive implications of these practices, schools are finding and creating more ways to support parents-school partnerships (Murray & Mereoiu, 2016; Newman et al., 2019). Partnerships between parents and school staff involve working together to align goals, behaviour norms and expectations for children. Schools use various strategies to strengthen these partnerships, such as newsletters to inform parents about school events and psychoeducational programmes that offer parenting strategies to support learning and develop problem-solving skills (Newman et al., 2019). Parental involvement in curriculum implementation is key in modern education systems, which emphasise holistic development through learner-centred approaches and competency-based curricula (Makena, 2023; Mwarari, Githui & Mwenje, 2020; Kihima, 2023). Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) is gaining traction worldwide as an innovative approach to education (Taliak et al., 2022; Muthuri, 2023; Abrami et al., 2020). It shifts the focus from content mastery to developing students' skills and competencies (Amutabi, 2019). CBC requires collaboration between teachers and parents to reinforce the learning process, encourage the practical application of skills, and ensure continuous assessment of students' progress (Amunga, Were & Ashioya, 2020; Wairimu, 2022; Njeru & Kirimi, 2023). However, challenges often arise due to differences in understanding, communication barriers, and varying levels of parental involvement, all of which can hinder the effective implementation of CBC. Over the past two decades, influenced by pressure from major international organisations such as UNICEF, UNESCO, the World Bank, and the East African Community, countries including Tanzania, Rwanda, Kenya, and Uganda have adopted Competency-Based Curricula in their basic education systems to align with 21st-century skills (Wambiya & Ogula, 2023). Tanzania introduced the competencybased approach in 2005 (Kafyulilo, Rugambuka & Moses, 2012; Godfrey, 2018), followed by Rwanda in 2015 (Nteziyaremye, Ndizeye & Murenzi, 2024) and Uganda in 2021 (Wambiya & Ogula, 2023). In Kenya, the Competency-Based Curriculum (CBC) was introduced in 2017 to replace the traditional 8-4 education system (Charles, Song & Khaing, 2022; Amutabi, 2019). This initiative aims to equip Kenyan children with the knowledge and skills required for the 21st century. CBC emphasises the acquisition of skills and competencies rather than rote learning (Kafu & Zigama, 2024). It promotes active learner engagement, creativity, critical thinking, and practical problem-solving (Garbacz et al., 2015). Several studies in Kenya have evaluated parental involvement in the implementation of CBC (Amunga et al., 2020; Rodgers & Alice, 2023; Mwarari et al., 2020; Wairimu, 2022). However, most of these studies have focused on students without disabilities. For children living

with disabilities, educational success relies heavily on consistent support both at school and home (Kunani, Tsindoli & Kafwa, 2025). Therefore, the challenge of this partnership is the lack of attention to the unique needs and experiences of children with disabilities, who require more specialised support and collaboration between parents and teachers. Parents of children with disabilities often face difficulties in understanding the CBC framework and how to support their child's learning at home, while teachers may struggle to provide the necessary guidance and resources for effective home-based learning. This gap in research highlights the need for more targeted studies and interventions to address the barriers to teacher-parent collaboration in supporting learners with disabilities under CBC. Hence, this study evaluated the challenges of teacher-parent partnership in the implementation of CBC for learners with special needs in Nyeri County, Kenya.

Theoretical Framework

The research was guided by Epstein's Model of Parental Involvement, which emphasises the importance of partnerships between schools and families to enhance student learning. Epstein (2007) created a framework focusing on the family, school, and community, with the child at the core. Developed by Joyce Epstein in 1995, the model comprises six typologies of parental involvement that delineate various ways families can engage in their children's education. These typologies provide a structured approach to fostering effective partnerships between educators and parents, essential for creating a supportive learning environment. The six typologies include parenting, communicating, volunteering, learning at home, decision-making, and community collaboration (Nathans & Revelle, 2018). Each typology addresses a different aspect of parental involvement, promoting a holistic approach to engaging families in the educational process. The first typology, parenting, emphasises the need for schools to assist families in developing parenting skills and understanding child development (Sorenson, 2019). Effective communication, the second typology, involves informing parents about school programmes and their children's progress and creating channels for feedback and dialogue (Newman et al., 2019). This reciprocal communication fosters a sense of partnership and shared responsibility for the child's education. Volunteering, the third typology, encourages parents to actively participate in school activities, enhancing their engagement and investment in their children's education. The fourth typology, learning at home, involves guiding families on how to engage in learning activities at home. This includes providing resources and strategies for supporting homework and curriculum-linked activities, which is particularly crucial for learners with special needs who may require additional support (Ihmeideh et al., 2020). The fifth typology, decision-making, highlights the importance of including parents in decision-making processes, allowing them to have a voice in governance and advocacy within the school community. This involvement empowers parents and acknowledges their role as partners in the educational process, ensuring that their perspectives are considered in policy and program development (Newman et al., 2019). Finally, the sixth typology, collaborating with the community, focuses on leveraging community resources to support students and families (Epstein et al., 2007).

Methodology

Research Design

The study utilised a descriptive survey design. This design is commonly used to gather information about a specific population or phenomenon at a particular point in time (Rahi, 2017). It involves the systematic collection of data through structured instruments such as questionnaires or interviews, which allow researchers to quantify the attitudes, perceptions, behaviours, or characteristics of participants.

Target Population

The target population in a study refers to the entire group of units from which data will be drawn to make inferences (Cox, 2013). As Gall, Borg, and Gall (2003) point out, a well-defined target population provides a foundation for establishing the study's validity and reliability. It also helps determine which cases are eligible or ineligible for inclusion in the study. Consequently, the target population for this research comprised 47 primary school teachers and 47 parents of learners with special needs in Nyeri County.

Demographic Information for Teachers

Table 1 presents the demographic information for the teachers who participated in the study, indicating their gender, age, highest level of education and teaching experience.

Table 1: Demographic Information for Teachers

Demographic info	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	21	44.7
	Female	26	55.3
What is your age	20-29 years	5	10.6
	30-39 years	14	29.8
	40-49 years	17	36.2
	50 years and above	11	23.4
Highest level of education	Diploma	8	17.0
	Bachelor's Degree	26	55.3
	Master's Degree	13	27.7
How many years of teaching experience do you have	Less than 5 years	6	12.8
	5-10 years	12	25.5
	11-15 years	16	34.0
	16 years and above	13	27.7

The demographic analysis in Table 1 revealed that most teachers were female (55.3%), and 44.7% were male. The age distribution indicates that most teachers fall within the 30-49 years range, with

36.2% in the 40-49 age group. Regarding educational qualifications, over half (55.3%) hold a Bachelor's degree, while 27.7% have a Master's degree. Regarding teaching experience, the majority (34.0%) have between 11-15 years of experience, indicating a well-established workforce with a good balance of experience levels.

Demographic Information for Parents

Table 2 presents the demographic information for the parents who participated in the study, indicating their gender, age, highest level of education and employment status. Table 2: Demographic Information for Parents

Demographic info	Variables	Frequency	Percentage
Gender	Male	19	40.4
	Female	28	59.6
What is your age	20-29 years	8	17.0
	30-39 years	15	31.9
	40-49 years	17	36.2
	50 years and above	7	14.9
Highest level of education	Primary School	10	21.3
	Secondary School	20	42.6
	Diploma/Certificate	11	23.4
	Bachelor's Degree	5	10.6
	Master's Degree	1	2.1
Employment Status	Employed	4	29.8
	Self-employed	31	65.9
	Unemployed:	12	25.5

According to Table 2, the majority of parents were female (59.6%), with the largest age group being between 40 and 49 (36.2%). A significant percentage of parents have a secondary-level education (42.6%) or lower. Most parents are self-employed (65.9%) or unemployed (25.5%).

Sample Size and Sampling Technique

Census sampling was conducted due to the small target population. Hence, all 47 teachers and 47 parents were sampled using the random sampling technique.

Data Collection Instruments

Data were collected using two primary instruments. A structured questionnaire was developed to gather quantitative data on teachers' perceptions of the TPP, their experiences with parental involvement, and the challenges they face in implementing the CBC. Additionally, semi-structured interviews were conducted with selected parent representatives to collect qualitative data regarding their understanding of their roles in the educational process and their experiences partnering with teachers.

Ethical Considerations

The study adhered to ethical standards by ensuring the confidentiality of participant information and obtaining informed consent before data collection. Participants were assured that their responses would be used solely for research purposes and that they had the right to withdraw from the study at any time without consequence.

Data Analysis

The collected data were edited for completeness and accuracy before analysis. Quantitative data from the teachers' questionnaires were analysed using the Statistical Package for the Social Sciences (SPSS) version 25, facilitating the computation of descriptive statistics such as means, frequencies, and percentages. The qualitative data obtained from the parent interviews were transcribed and thematically analysed to identify common themes and patterns related to the TPP and its effectiveness. The study results were presented using frequency tables, charts, and graphs to illustrate the quantitative findings clearly. Qualitative findings were summarised thematically.

Results and discussion

Teacher-Parent Partnership (TPP) in CBC implementation

Statements	Strongly Disagree (SD)	Disagree (D)	Neutral (N)	Agree (A)	Strongly Agree (SA)
Parents are actively involved in their children's education under the CBC	9 (19.1%)	18 (38.3%)	8 (17.0%)	9 (19.1%)	3 (6.4%)
I feel that parents understand their role in supporting the CBC for learners with special needs	15 (31.9%)	18 (38.3%)	7 (14.9%)	5 (10.6%)	2 (4.3%)
Parents regularly provide feedback on their children's learning progress at home.	16 (34.0%)	17 (36.2%)	8 (17.0%)	5 (10.6%)	1 (2.1%)
The school has clear policies guiding Teacher-Parent Partnerships in CBC implementation	9 (19.1%)	12 (25.5%)	13 (27.7%)	8 (17.0%)	5 (10.6%)
Lack of parental involvement is a significant barrier to the successful implementation of CBC	2 (4.3%)	8 (17.0%)	6 (12.8%)	18 (38.3%)	13 (27.7%)
There is a need for a TPP manual to guide interactions with parents in CBC implementation	0 (0%)	1 (2.1%)	2 (4.3%)	14 (29.8%)	30 (63.8%)

Teachers were asked to rate their level of agreement with the following statements about the Teacher-Parent Partnership (TPP) in CBC implementation. The findings are presented in Table 3.

Table 3: Teachers' Ratings of Agreement on Statements Regarding the TPP in CBC Implementation

As indicated in Table 3, 38.3% of teachers disagree that parents are actively involved in their children's education under the CBC, while 19.1% agree. Additionally, 31.9% strongly disagree that parents understand their role in supporting the CBC for learners with special needs, whereas only 10.6% agree. Feedback from parents on their children's learning progress is also a concern, with 34.0% strongly disagreeing that it occurs regularly. While some ambiguity exists regarding school policies guiding TPP, 27.7% of teachers remain neutral. Interestingly, 66.0% of respondents agree or strongly agree that the lack of parental involvement is a barrier to CBC implementation, and an overwhelming 63.8% express a strong need for a TPP manual to facilitate interactions with parents. The findings of this study align with other studies that have explored parental awareness of the new curriculum. Mwarari et al. (2020) found that a lack of induction and sensitisation for parents on CBC has challenged its implementation. They emphasise that engaging parents in learning about CBC is key to its success. Similarly, Wairimu (2022) noted that a lack of parental involvement in school activities hinders the actualisation of the new curriculum. Furthermore, the Kenya Institute of Curriculum Development (KICD) emphasises parental empowerment and engagement as a guiding principle of CBC (KICD, 2019).

Effectiveness of the current TPP in achieving the objectives of the CBC

Teachers were asked to evaluate the effectiveness of the current Teacher-Parent Partnership in achieving the objectives of the CBC for learners with special needs.

Table 4: Teachers' Ratings of the Effectiveness of the Current TPP in Achieving CBC Objectives for Learners with Special Needs

	Frequency	Percentage
Very ineffective	5	10.6
Ineffective:	12	25.5
Neutral	15	31.9
Effective	11	23.4
Very effective	4	8.4

Results indicated that the majority of teachers (31.9%) remained neutral about its effectiveness, while 25.5% considered it ineffective, 23.4% felt the partnership was effective, and 8.4% rated it as very effective. This distribution indicates that while some teachers recognise the partnership's potential, there is considerable room for improvement in its implementation.

Parents rating on the effectiveness of TPP in helping their child progress under the CBC

Figure 3: Illustrates parents' views on the effectiveness of the current support in supporting their child's progress under the CBC.

Figure 3: Parents' Ratings of the Effectiveness of the Current Teacher-Parent Partnership (TPP) in Supporting Child Progress under the CBC

Results indicated in Figure 3 that the majority of parents (34.0%) remained neutral about its effectiveness. Meanwhile, 27.7% felt that the partnership was effective, 12.8% rated the partnership as very ineffective, 19.1% considered it ineffective, and 6.4% rated it as very effective.

Parents' perceptions regarding the opportunities provided by the school for engaging with teachers about the CBC

In an interview response, one parent remarked, "While I have had some opportunities to meet with teachers, I often feel that more regular meetings would help us understand the CBC better and how to support our children at home." This sentiment captures the essence of the concerns voiced by those who feel a gap in engagement opportunities, suggesting a need for more structured interaction between parents and teachers to enhance collaboration in supporting learners.

Challenges faced by parents in supporting their children's education at home under the CompetenceBased Curriculum (CBC)

The findings reveal several significant challenges faced by parents in supporting their children's education at home under the CBC, the most prominent being a **lack of understanding of the curriculum**. The majority of the parents reported that they do not fully understand the CBC, making it difficult for them to assist their children effectively. One parent expressed this frustration, saying, "The curriculum is new, and we were never taught in this way. I often feel lost when trying to help my child with assignments." This lack of understanding hinders their ability to support their children's learning, particularly for learners with special needs who require additional guidance.

Many parents are also balancing work and family responsibilities, which limits the time they can dedicate to their children's education. One parent remarked, "I work long hours, and by the time I get home, it's difficult to sit down and go through everything with my child. I want to help, but time is a big

issue." This suggests that even though parents may be willing to participate in their child's education, their schedules pose a significant barrier.

The **lack of resources**, such as learning materials, was cited by most parents as another impediment. Many parents struggle to provide the necessary materials for their children to complete their assignments at home. One parent shared, "Sometimes the teachers expect us to have certain materials for the assignments, but we don't have access to these resources. It makes it hard to support my child properly." This points to a need for schools to ensure that parents are equipped with the appropriate resources to facilitate learning at home.

Poor communication from the school was also noted by several parents, who felt that the school does not provide clear or consistent updates about their child's progress or the expectations of CBC. One parent commented, "There are times when I feel like I don't know what's happening in school. We only get called for meetings once in a while, but there's little communication in between." This lack of communication exacerbates the other challenges parents face, as they are often unsure of how to assist their children without regular updates from teachers.

Lastly, several parents reported encountering other challenges, including personal issues that affect their ability to be involved in their child's education. One parent mentioned, "I'm struggling with some personal issues right now, and it's hard to focus on my child's education while dealing with these challenges."

Challenges that teachers face when working with parents in the implementation of the CompetenceBased Curriculum (CBC) for learners with special needs

Teachers expressed concern that many parents do not fully understand their responsibilities under the CBC framework, especially in supporting their children at home. As one teacher noted, "Most parents think their role ends at paying school fees. They don't realise that their involvement at home is key to their child's success in CBC." This gap in understanding prevents parents from engaging meaningfully in their child's education. According to Hoover-Dempsey et al. (2005), parental engagement is often hindered by parents' limited awareness of contributing to their child's education beyond financial support. This misunderstanding is particularly problematic in the context of CBC, which requires active involvement in the learning process at home, a key factor for learners with special needs. Studies in the U.S. and Australia have also shown that when parents do not understand their supportive role in education, it directly impacts the efficacy of competency-based learning models (Henderson & Mapp, 2002).

Another challenge teachers frequently mention is that **parents focus solely on paying fees**, neglecting other vital aspects of their child's learning process. Teachers highlight that many parents perceive their financial contribution as their primary obligation, leaving little room for academic or behavioural support involvement. One teacher shared, "Parents often tell us, 'We've paid the fees, so it's your job to teach.' But CBC requires parents to be part of the learning process, especially for children with special needs." This misconception about their role hinders effective Teacher-Parent Partnerships

(TPP), which are essential for the holistic development of learners under the CBC. This behaviour aligns with findings by Goodall and Montgomery (2014), which reveal that parents often believe their financial role supersedes other forms of involvement. As a result, they may disengage from key activities like providing emotional or academic support, which are vital under competency-based frameworks.

Teachers also reported that many parents struggle to find time to engage with them or attend school-related activities, making collaboration difficult. One teacher explained, "Parents tell us they are busy with work or other responsibilities, and we rarely get to meet or communicate effectively. Without regular engagement, it's hard to address the needs of learners with special needs." This lack of interaction limits parents' ability to provide ongoing support at home and collaborate with teachers to monitor their child's progress. The findings align with those of Epstein et al. (2009), showing that parents' busy schedules often impede their ability to attend school meetings or communicate regularly with teachers. In Canada, for example, teachers report similar challenges where parents' limited availability reduces opportunities for meaningful dialogue and problem-solving concerning their child's needs (Pushor & Ruitenberg, 2005). The lack of time for such interactions directly hinders the successful implementation of CBC, which demands consistent and open communication between educators and parents.

The **lack of proper communication channels** between parents and teachers is another concern. Teachers noted that communication is often inconsistent or non-existent, making it difficult to keep parents informed about their child's learning needs and progress. As one teacher put it, "We don't have a consistent way of communicating with parents. Sometimes we rely on meetings, but not all parents attend. We need more structured communication systems." This lack of communication contributes to the disconnect between home and school, further complicating the implementation of CBC. Research by Pushor & Ruitenberg, (2005) highlights that ineffective communication is a common barrier in school-parent partnerships, as schools often lack the resources to maintain consistent dialogue with parents. In CBC contexts, where continuous feedback is key for monitoring progress, this communication gap becomes even more problematic. Studies in Sweden and Finland have also indicated that when communication systems are fragmented, parents are less likely to stay informed about their child's learning needs and progress, further complicating the implementation of special needs education (Hujala et al., 2009).

Strategies to improve Teacher-Parent Partnerships in CBC implementation

Several teachers recommended developing a **comprehensive TPP manual**. Teachers believe that having a clear and structured guide outlining the roles and responsibilities of educators and parents would provide the necessary framework for effective collaboration. One teacher remarked, "A manual would be a reference point for everyone involved. It could clarify expectations and provide practical advice on how parents can engage with their children's learning." This structured approach would help ensure all parties understand their roles, fostering a more collaborative environment.

Many teachers emphasised the importance of equipping parents with the knowledge and skills to support their children's education effectively. One teacher stated, "Workshops would empower parents with the tools to assist their children at home. Understanding the CBC framework better would enable them to engage more meaningfully." This training could address common misconceptions about parental involvement and provide strategies for supporting learners, especially those with special needs.

Creating **consistent communication channels** between teachers and parents is essential for improving TPP. Teachers highlighted the need for regular and structured updates on student progress, school activities, and ways parents can contribute to their child's learning. As one teacher said, "We need to establish reliable ways to communicate, whether through newsletters, WhatsApp groups, or scheduled phone calls. Consistent communication keeps everyone informed and involved." This initiative would enhance transparency and build trust and rapport between teachers and parents.

Involving parents in **decision-making and feedback processes** is another essential strategy teachers suggest. They believe that when parents have a voice in school-related decisions, it promotes a sense of ownership and responsibility towards their child's education. One teacher commented, "When parents are included in discussions about curriculum changes or school policies, they feel valued and are more likely to engage actively. It also helps us understand their perspectives and concerns better." This inclusion can create a more collaborative atmosphere where parents feel empowered to contribute to their child's learning journey.

Teachers' opinions on the role of parents in supporting the CBC for learners with special needs

Teachers believe that parental involvement in homework helps children understand the material better and strengthens the learning process. One teacher articulated, "When parents engage in homework, it sends a message to the child that education is important. This support at home can significantly impact their understanding of the curriculum." This engagement not only aids academic achievement but also promotes a positive attitude towards learning.

Teachers also highlighted that open lines of communication can provide valuable insights into a child's learning experience and needs. One teacher noted, "When parents contact us, it allows for a collaborative approach to education. We can work together to address any child's challenges." This proactive communication helps ensure that both parties are aligned to support the child's learning journey.

Teachers further emphasised the importance of parents **attending school meetings and workshops on CBC**. Such participation is key for parents to stay informed about educational strategies and expectations related to the CBC. A teacher expressed, "Workshops are a great opportunity for parents to learn more about the curriculum and how they can help their children. When informed, parents feel more confident in supporting their kids." Active involvement in school events

promotes a stronger connection between home and school, reinforcing the shared commitment to the child's education.

Relationship between the Frequency of teacher communications with parents and parents' participation in school activities

A Chi-Square Test of Independence was utilised to determine if there is a significant association between the frequency of teacher communications with parents and parents' participation in school activities. The findings are presented in Table 4.

Table 4: Chi-Square Test of Independence Results

	Value	df	Asymptotic Significance (2-sided)
Pearson Chi-Square	15.36	4	.004
N of Valid cases	4		

Table 4 results indicate a significant statistical relationship between the frequency of teacher communications with parents and parents' participation in school activities ($\chi^2=15.36, p<0.05$). This finding suggests that as teachers' communication frequency increases, parents are more likely to engage in school activities. A study by Indimuli (2022) in Nairobi City County found that parental communication was a significant predictor of academic achievement, which is often linked to overall parental involvement in school activities.

Conclusion

Results indicate that while many teachers report occasional interactions with parents, a significant percentage communicate infrequently, correlating with lower levels of parental involvement in school activities. The data also reveal that both teachers and parents recognise the need for improved partnerships, with a significant number of teachers expressing concerns about the lack of understanding among parents regarding their roles in supporting the CBC. While parental involvement is crucial at all stages of a child's education, the most critical level of involvement, especially within the CBC in Kenya, is at the foundational/early primary level. This stage lays the groundwork for lifelong learning and skills development, which are central goals of the CBC. Moreover, challenges such as time constraints, insufficient resources, and inadequate communication further hinder effective teacher-parent collaboration. Addressing these challenges is key to enhancing the educational experience for learners with special needs. Schools should establish regular and structured communication mechanisms to keep parents informed about their child's progress and school activities. This will promote transparency and encourage active engagement. Furthermore, there is a need for schools to implement workshops to educate parents about the CBC framework and their roles in supporting their children's education. Providing practical strategies will empower parents to engage meaningfully in their child's learning process. Additionally, schools should implement systems for collecting regular feedback from parents regarding their experiences and challenges in supporting their children's

education. This feedback can inform ongoing improvements in communication strategies and partnership initiatives.

References

Amunga, J., Were, D., & Ashioya, I. (2020). The Teacher-Parent Nexus in the Competency-based curriculum success equation in Kenya. *International Journal of Educational Administration and Policy Studies*, 12(1), 60-76.

Amutabi, M. N. (2019). Competency-based curriculum (CBC) and the end of an era in Kenya's education sector and implications for development: Some empirical reflections. *Journal of Popular Education in Africa*, 3(10), 45-66.

Boonk, L., Gijsselaers, H. J., Ritzen, H., & Brand-Gruwel, S. (2018). A review of the relationship between parental involvement indicators and academic achievement. *Educational research review*, 24, 10-30.

Charles, K., Song, Z., & Khaing, T. (2022).

Factors Affecting the Implementation of Competency-Based Curriculum in Lower Secondary Schools in Uganda: A Systematic Literature Review.

Cosso, J., von Suchodoletz, A., & Yoshikawa, H. (2022). Effects of parental involvement programs on young children's academic and social-emotional outcomes: A meta-analysis. *Journal of Family Psychology*, 36(8), 1329.

Cox, B. G. (2013). Target Population.

Gall, M. D., Borg, W. R., & Gall, J. P. (2003). *Educational research: An introduction*. (7th Ed.). White Plains, New York: Longman.

Epstein, J. L. (2007). Improving family and community involvement in secondary schools. *Principal leadership*, 8(2), 16-22.